

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN FORMING THE COMPETENCES OF STUDENTS' INTEREST IN NATIONAL CRAFT

Roila Yuldoshvoyevna Xaydarova

Second-year master's student in the field of theory and methodology of education and training
(technological education), TSPU named after Nizami

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Abstract. *This article talks about the importance and effectiveness of using pedagogical technologies in the formation of students' competences of interest in national handicrafts.*

Keywords: *labor education, crafts, national crafts, competence of interest, "Boomerang", "Cluster", "Dividing into groups".*

Craftsmanship is a type of industry based on individual and manual labor, using national-traditional small goods production; is the general name of the professions in which such products are made. It was widespread until the emergence of large-scale industrial production, and some areas were preserved even after that. It still occupies an important place in the national economy of less developed countries. Uzbekistan is one of these countries.

Today, you can see the most attractive works of craftsmen in the field of crafts and its various types across the territory of the country. In order to further expand the number of such jobs and the ranks of skilled craftsmen, it is necessary to organize labor education, i.e., technology science with deep content in general education schools, and to awaken students' interest in crafts and national crafts in these lessons is very important.

In order to arouse the interest of schoolchildren in crafts, it is first of all necessary to find out with them what kind of crafts they are interested in with the help of various pedagogical technologies. With this, it is possible to facilitate the formation of a suitable set of methods for organizing appropriate practical training and circle processes for students to engage in a particular type of handicraft.

It is appropriate to be aware of its content, purpose and mission before using pedagogical technologies to arouse the interest of students of general education in national crafts.

The purpose of pedagogical technology is to ensure the necessary effectiveness of the educational process in the conditions of public education and to ensure that students achieve the intended results of their studies. Its main task is to meaningfully create educational processes that ensure sufficient effectiveness of teaching "ordinary" pedagogues in the conditions of mass

education. Based on these, various pedagogical technologies and methods can be used in the organization of labor education.

Examples of effective methods include "Cluster", "Boomerang", "Brainstorming", "Problem-based learning", and "Turntable". Such methods help to collect information about the interests of students in a more specific form. In addition, it is possible to organize "pedagogical games" based on these methods. It is also appropriate to give importance to the types of lessons in the procedures. For example, using the demonstration method in explaining a new topic, creating problematic situations, organizing lessons full of discussions and debates, sharing students' opinions, developing their creative activities, knowledge and skills related to folk crafts. The use of national traditions in development, the formation of independent and creative thinking, and the development of the desire for innovation are among the types of lessons rich in diversity. The above-mentioned methods are taught during the "Labor Education (Technology)" lesson and during the training of knowledge and skills related to folk crafts. Therefore, it is important to select, analyze and analyze the content for the lesson, to be able to apply the acquired knowledge during the practical period, based on the instructions.

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